

ISic0419

I.Sicily inscription 0419

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

natural rock

Object

Building (store-room?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Euryelos; four subterranean crypts

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica Castello Eurialo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 190-200 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. CIIINbbb
2. CIIINbbb
3. CINNb
4. CIIINbbbb

Apparatus

Placeholder text based upon the transcription of Kaible in IG

Translation

Commentary

Previous editors have been uncertain whether these are numerals or letters, and whether Latin or Greek. The most recent edition by Mertens, after consultation with Maria Letizia Lazzarini, suggests that these are acrophonic numerals (Greek) of the fourth or third century BC. A revised edition will follow

Digital identifiers:

TM 491648
EDCS 21900482
PHI 140311

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0017 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7139 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)
- Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7139a = p.992 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)
- Schubring, J. 1861-1867. Akrä-Palazzolo. Eine topographisch-archäologische Skizze. *Jahrbücher für classische Philologie.* Vierter Supplementband: 659-673. At 671-672 tab. no.8
- Beste, H.-J., Mertens, D. 2015. Die Mauern von Syrakus. Das Kastell Euryalos und die Befestigung der Epipolai. *Deutsches Archäologisches Institut Rom Sonderschriften Band 18.* Wiesbaden. At 147-148 Abb.179a-d

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0419. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335596>